

STUDIES IN ENZYMES. PART III. AMYLASES FROM SOME INDIAN TUBERS

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Active diastatic enzyme occurs in (a) sweet potato, white variety (*Ipomoea batatas*) (b) Arvi (*Colocasia antiquorum*) (c) Banda (*Zingiber cassumunar*) and (d) Zimikand (*Amorphophallus campanulatus*).

The enzyme can be prepared by drying the material and taking the water extract of the dried meal followed by dialysis, precipitation with ammonium sulphate and alcohol and also by pressing the tubers and using the extracted juice for dialysis and precipitation. The extracted juice does not lose its amylolytic activity if preserved in cold under toluene.

The amylase occurring in sweet potato (white variety) resembles malt amylase and is saccharogen or β -amylase, whereas the amylase occurring in Arvi and Banda resembles the *Asp. oryzae* amylase and is

In a previous work the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **18**, 407; 1942, **19**, 121) has studied the amylase from the tuberous root of the herb Kaseru (*Scirpus Grossus*, Linn). Amongst the tubers potato amylase has been very extensively investigated by many authors. Giri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.* 1934, **11**, 339) extended the knowledge of a similar tuber-amylase by investigating the amylase occurring in sweet potato (red variety). Agarwal (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1937, **7**, 29; 1938, **8**, 384) found the presence of β -amylase in water chestnut (*Tropa bispinosa*, Roxb). The optimum p_n and temperatures of amylases from different sources differ to a very considerable extent. Recent work has shown (Kuhn, *Annalen*, 1925, **443**, 1) that there are two definite types of amylases, α and β occurring in different sources.

Amylases have been finding increasing use in the industry and are extensively used in canning for clarifying jellies. In silk industry it is used for de-gumming, in paper and textiles it is applied for converting starch to a soluble form for de-sizing and is being sold under various trade names. Indirectly it is applied in brewing, and in the production of *miso* and *taka* diastase and in medicine.

In view of the increased demand for different amylases it would be only opportune to search out new raw materials whence this important enzyme can be tapped.

The present investigation relates to the presence of amylases in cheap raw materials extensively cultivated in India commonly as food vegetables. The commonly occurring tubers Arvi (*Colocasia antiquorum*), Banda (*Zingiber cassumunar*) and Zimikand (*Amorphophallus campanulatus*) have been investigated along with the sweet potato (*white variety*) and results compared with malt diastase prepared under similar conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation and Detection of Amylase from the Tubers.—A bazar sample of the tubers was peeled and washed in water and softened in a mortar and pestle. The juice was expelled in a tincture press and preserved under toluene and tested for the presence of amylase by Linter method.

The figures in Table I indicate a definite presence of amylase in the juices extracted from the above tubers. It was possible to preserve the juices in the cold at 0° — 4° under toluene for a period of one year without much loss in amylolytic activity except in the case of Zimikand.

TABLE I

Source.	Lintar value.	Lintar value after storing for one year at 0°.
Sweet potato extract (<i>Ipomoea batatas</i>)	130	125
Arvi extract (<i>Colocasia antiquorum</i>)	65	62
Banda extract (<i>Zingiber cassumunar</i>)	72	68
Zimikand extract (<i>Amorphophallus campanulatus</i>)	35	19
Germinated barley or malt extract	55	52

A more convenient method of preserving the enzyme was by converting the tubers to a dried powder. The tubers were minced in a chopper and the tissues dried in enamelled trays without allowing them to ferment. The material was ground to a fine powder and sieved through a fine mesh and preserved in closed bottles. The enzyme was extracted in 20% alcohol solution and tested.

Procedure.—Lintar's soluble starch was used as a substrate in all experiments. The hydrogen ion concentration of the mixtures was adjusted by Walpole's acetate buffers between p_H range 3.0-6.5 and Sørensen's phosphate buffers for higher ranges. The enzyme solutions were obtained by suitably diluting the extracts obtained from different stages of purification. Activity was measured by obtaining the CuO precipitated by the converted invert sugars with Fehling's solution as recommended by Sherman, Kendall and Clark (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **32**, 1073). The dry matter in the solution of the enzyme used in the reaction was determined in each case by drying an aliquot portion of the extracts at 105° to a constant weight. The reactions were carried out at constant temperature in an electrically controlled thermostat. The digestions were carried out in Erlenmeyer flasks with 100 c.c. of a 2% soluble Lintar starch solution, enzyme solutions, and buffers.

Detection of Amylase in the dried Powders.—The powder (50 g.) in each case was extracted with 500 g. of pure distilled water, buffered at p_H 5.4, triturating in a mortar and occasionally shaking at 37° for 24 hours. To avoid contamination and to facilitate extraction 20% redistilled alcohol was mixed with water. The extracts, thus obtained, were allowed to settle in the cold at 4°, decanted, filtered and used in the experiment.

As the extracts contained soluble sugars a blank was also taken in each case to allow for the glucose due to extract and starch which was subtracted from the total weight of CuO obtained to get the reaction due to the enzyme action.

TABLE II

Extract taken.	Starch solution (2%) = 100 c.c. Buffer ($p_H = 5.4$), 10 c.c. Enzyme solution = 4 c.c. Temp. of reaction = 36.5° ± 0.1°. Time of reaction = 1 hr.			
	Total solids in the extract.	CuO blank.	CuO due to extract.	CuO due to enzyme.
Sweet potato	0.2512 g.	0.4482 g.	1.2563 g.	0.8081 g.
Arvi	0.5442	0.2800	0.8243	0.5443
Banda	0.4604	0.2365	0.6969	0.4614
Zimikand	0.1430	0.2012	0.2581	0.0469

The presence of amylase was indicated in each of the above materials and sweet potato was found to be the richest amongst them. The activity of the amylase from Zimikand was found to be the least both in case of its pressed juice as well as the powdered starch indicating that it is not a rich source of enzyme.

Purification of the Enzyme.—The most authentic method employed for the purification was that employed by Sherman, Caldwell and Doebbeling (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, **104**, 501). Their method was to fractionate the extracts of barley-malt with ammonium sulphate followed by dialysis and repeated fractional precipitation with alcohol.

Dialysis.—A preliminary dialysis was employed using collodion membrane to get rid of the adhering sugars and salts from the extract at 15°.

TABLE III

Period of dialysis.	Zimikand		Sweet potato		Arvi		Banda	
	Total solids in 5 c.c.	CuO due to enzyme.	Total solids in 5 c.c.	CuO due to enzyme.	Total solids in 5 c.c.	CuO due to enzyme.	Total solids in 5 c.c.	CuO due to enzyme.
Original extract	0'4532 g.	0'5600 g.	0'2512 g	0'8081 g.	0'5142 g.	0'6064 g.	0'4132 g.	0'9300 g.
7 hours	0'2351	0'4513	0'1463	0'7512	0'3241	0'5014	0'3151	0'7200
4 "	0'1932	0'4615	0'0873	0'7613	0'2140	0'5132	0'2512	0'7100
5 "	0'1083	0'4732	0'0788	0'7422	0'2013	0'5200	0'1460	0'6900
6 "	0'096	0'4700	0'0780	0'9754	0'1465	0'5215	0'090	0'6800
8 "	0'097	0'4530	0'0780	0'9700	0'1460	0'5000	0'091	0'6573

It was found that after six hours' dialysis the purification was effected and further dialysis caused loss of the enzymic activity. So for next batches six hours' dialysis was employed.

Precipitation with Ammonium Sulphate and Alcohol.—On the basis of the findings in the previous paper by the author (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **19**, 121) 400 c.c. of the dialysed extract were taken and 160 g. of pure ammonium sulphate added. The solution was well stirred and left in the frigidaire for 70 hours. The supernatant liquid was filtered off by upward microfiltration and solids washed with alcohol and ether. The solids were then dissolved in distilled water, buffered at p_H 5'6 using Walpole's acetate buffer and dialysed free from sulphate. The enzyme preparations were then further purified by precipitation with alcohol.

The dialysed solution in each case was mixed with enough absolute alcohol to obtain a strength of 50% by volume and any precipitate obtained removed by upward filtration. The strength of the solution was then further raised to 75% alcohol. The precipitates thrown out were separated and dissolved in double distilled water. A portion dissolved in double distilled water was used for determination of optimum p_H . The activity of the purified enzyme preparations is given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Enzyme = 2 c.c. Starch (2% soln.) = 80 c.c.
Buffer = 20 c.c. Time of reaction = 1 hour.
Temp. = 37° ± 0'1°.

Source of enzyme.	Dry weight of enzyme.	CuO due to enzyme
Sweet potato	0'0071 g	0'8941
Arvi	0'0281	0'2475
Banda	0'0324	0'2782
Zimikand	0'0301	0'1789
Malt	0'0628	0'2883

TABLE V

Starch (2% soln.) = 80 c.c. Buffer = 20 c.c.
Time of reaction = 1 hour.
Temp. = 37° ± 0'1°.

Source of enzyme.	Optimum temperature.	Optimum p_H .
Sweet potato	50-55°	5'0-5'2
Banda	55°	5'6-6'0
Arvi	55-60°	6'0
Malt extract	55°	5'0-5'1

The optimum of Zimikand could not be determined due to the purified preparation being lost and fresh tubers being not available till the next season.

From the study on the optimum p_H it can be seen that the optimum p_H of sweet potato (white variety) resembles malt amylase as reported by Giri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 339) and is saccharogen amylase (β -amylase). But the p_H of Arvi and Banda have their optimum between 5.6-6.0. Their optimum p_H resembles more the α -amylases occurring in *Aspergillus Oryzae* which as reported by Caldwell and Tyler (*J. Amer Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **53**, 2316), lies at p_H 5.3 to 5.5 at 40° with 0.01M-acetate buffer. The optimum temperature is 55° in all cases.

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